

Memory as a Process of Woman in the Novel of Atwood's *Alias Grace*

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P.Murali Arasan

*Assistant Professor of English
Devanga Arts College (Autonomous), Aruppukottai*

Abstract

Margaret Atwood depicts life memory as a process, a journey into one's self that results in self-realization, self-assertion and reconciliation. She brings out the sufferings of women under her writings portrait of Canadian Women. Atwood's Alias Grace (1997), the central character, Grace Marks who is accused of double murders spends nearly twenty nine years in the penitentiary. Grace, at the beginning, is taken to a lunatic asylum for her madness and amnesia. Later she is transferred to Kingston Penitentiary and she remains there for long. Consequent on Dr. Simon's interviews, Grace is proved to be innocent. In his meetings with Grace, Simon employs several experiments, and methods to recover her lost memory but all his efforts go in vain. At last, Simon becomes mad, and he leaves a medical report in support of Grace's pardon. Remaining in the penitentiary for twenty nine years, she scorns the codes of patriarchy. By marrying Jamie Walsh at the age of forty five, she not only fulfills her desire for owning a home and doing the quilt work but also caters to the desire of Mary Whitney, another victim of the same society.

Keywords: Lunatic asylum, fits and hysteria, melting-pot, amnesia, self-realization, self-assertion and reconciliation.

Margaret Atwood depicts life memory as a process, a journey into one's self that results in self-realization, self-assertion and reconciliation. She, while establishing the Canadian identity in the making of Canadian literature, discusses the place of women under the British empirical colonization and the influence of Americanism. Atwood brings out the sufferings of women under her writings. She can be used on the ground that they are not only feminist writers of the Commonwealth nations but also are involved in the plight of the marginalized women in their writings. While Atwood deals with the life of Canadian women.

Atwood's *Alias Grace* (1997), the central character, Grace Marks who is accused of double murders spends nearly twenty nine years in the penitentiary. Grace, an Irish immigrant, at the age of sixteen works as a maid in the household of a gentleman called Thomas Kinnear. Together with James McDermott, Mr. Kinnear's stable man, she is alleged to have convicted the murder of her employer and his mistress, Nancy Montgomery. McDermott is sentenced to death but Grace escapes death due to her lawyer's brilliant defense. Her sentence is commuted to life imprisonment. Initially, she is sent

to a lunatic asylum in Toronto for her frequent fits and hysteria. Though she is convicted of the crime, she pleads not guilty and her crime is not proved.

Atwood fictionalizes the true story of Grace Marks in this novel. Along with the historical characters, she depicts Dr. Jordan, a New Englander, and an expert in treating patients suffering from amnesia. He tries to discover the truth from Grace Marks during his psychoanalytical sessions held in the Governor's sewing room. Using detective methods, he attempts to show whether Grace actually committed the crime or she was insane at the time of murder. Atwood gives a three-layered story in *Alias Grace*. Grace's narration about her life comes as the prime story. Dr. Simon Jordan's attempts to find out the truth about Grace unfold the possibilities of a second version of the story about Grace. The third layer of story is fabricated with facts and fiction. Atwood fictionalizes Grace's story based on historical events. While narrating her story to Dr. Simon Jordan, Grace Marks is selective in phrasing the events. She accuses the society in spite of her being accused. She feels that her society wants to see her as a celebrated murderess, and later she accepts the title, 'Murderess'. "Murderer is merely brutal. It's like a hammer, or a lump of metal. I would rather be a murderess than a murderer, if those are the only choices." (25)

In this novel, Grace, a child among four brothers and four sisters, loses her mother at an early age. Her mason father, who turns out to be a drunkard, starts exploiting the labour of his children. He makes Grace work as a servant-maid since her childhood. She serves nearly six masters. When she works at Mrs. Alderman Parkinson's house with Mary Whitney, she learns more about men and the world. Due to the large size of her family and the drunken nature of her father she sacrifices all pleasures related to childhood. She thinks of killing one or two of her brothers and sisters: "I might just push one or two of them over, and then there would not be so many to feed, nor so many clothes to wash." (124) Against her wishes to be free from the household duties Grace has to start her career as a maid. After the death of her mother she is forced to be in the custody of her drunken father who in turn expects money from her. She accepts Mary Whitney as her model. In fact, Mary, who teaches her about moving with men and other female problems, dies of abortion. Once she warns Grace: "at once you are found with a man in your room, you are the guilty one, no matter how they get it." (231)

Having learnt several lessons from Mary Whitney, Grace gradually develops into a strong woman. When Mr. Haraghy, her employer, attempts to misbehave, she thinks of Mary's advice about kicking between the legs. In his letter to Dr. Edward Murchie, Dr. Simon writes about Grace: ".....the gentle Grace, having been hardened in the fire now for some fifteen years, will be a very hard nut to crack" (61). Her real story remains at one side; the other story she fabricates, as she quilts in the Governor's wife's sewing room when she answers Dr. Simon. Atwood, through Grace, interrogates the nature of forgetting, the secrets of human soul and the art of the patchwork quilt. She carefully tells the past to Dr. Simon as she confesses in the trial. In this context it is worth quoting Elaine Showalter who argues that patchwork, "an art of making do and eking out" that reflects the fragmentation of women's time, has come to replace the melting-pot as the central metaphor of American cultural identity." (Rogerson 5)

Grace, having acquired the name Mary Whitney, not only pays a dubious identity, but also narrates different stories about her life. Her quilting art enables her to withhold her secrets from her male inquisitor Dr. Simon, as he attempts to recover her lost memories of the crime using the traditional method of suggestion by association. Her art of sewing gives Grace a voice through which she can articulate her secrets. It is a story of a woman who has no means of proving the truth due to the biased society and due to a section of society that deserves no sympathy. Grace Marks' experiences with the male dominated society, inclusive of her father, make her remain silent and pretend to be mad in order to wreak vengeance on the society. As she loses all faith in her father she is even prepared to kill him: I had begun to have thoughts about the iron cooking pot, and how heavy it was; and if it should happen to drop on him while he was asleep, it could

smash his skull open, and kill him dead, and I would say it was an accident;.....(149) Alongside her own sufferings in the hands of her father, Grace thinks of the pains of Mary Whitney and Nancy Montgomery, the mistress of Mr. Kinnear, who suffer in the hands of men. Mary Whitney, though she introduces various safety measures to Grace, becomes a victim of male chauvinism. Her lover, who is not known to any body, impregnates her. To escape the biological trap, Mary goes to a doctor. After returning from the doctor, she gets profuse bleeding and dies the same night. Her unknown lover creates an awkward opinion about men in Grace's mind. Nancy who lives as a mistress in the house of Mr. Kinnear wants to become Kinnear's wife, but Mr. Kinnear tells her that a mistress is a mistress. The defeats faced by Mary and Nancy force Grace to act on society vengefully.

When James McDermott, the stable man of Mr. Kinnear decides to kill both Nancy and Mr. Kinnear, Grace has to go hand in hand with McDermott in executing the murder, for otherwise he would kill her too. James plans to kill Nancy for the reason that she has removed him from service; and he wants to kill Mr. Kinnear as thereby he can gather all the valuable things from him. James compels Grace to accompany him in committing the murder. She reveals this to Dr. Simon: Cried, sir, in the Kitchen. I did not want to leave, and I had no new situation to get to. It had been so sudden; I'd had no time to seek for one. And I was afraid she would not pay me after all, and send me off with no reference, and then what would I do? And McDermott feared the same. (359)

In the course of their regular meetings in the Prison Governor's wife's sewing room, Grace and Dr. Simon develop a liking towards each other. But Dr. Simon immediately drops the idea as she is a female prisoner and an amnesiac too. By bringing back Dora, the servant maid, and helping the land lady, Simon proves himself to be a patron of women. With a soft corner and hope, Simon starts his interrogation with Grace very carefully. But in the course of their interviews Grace's way of telling past irritates him and he declares: "To speak plainly, her madness was a fraud and an imposture....She is an accomplished actress and a most practiced liar." (81)

While narrating her story Grace keeps sewing the quilts. When Dr. Simon requests her to reveal everything, she says, "A lady might conceal things, as she has her reputation to lose; but I am beyond that." (104) Simon, with his own apprehensions, examines her with all admiration as she is young and beautiful. Then, the comment on Grace from another psychoanalyst by name Verringe that she is innocent, Simon doubts very much. He thinks that every one believes in the innocence of Grace only due to her outward appearance. Simon, during to the kind of response he receives from Grace, identifies Grace as a 'negative female variety'. He thinks, "She can deny and reject much more easily than she can affirm or accept." (421) He also finds in her a foil to Mr. Mac Kengie, Grace Mark's lawyer. The lawyer in turn admits that Grace is a "Lady of silences." (433) Simon goes to the graves where Mary Whitney is buried and finds the grave with no dates on it. He recounts, "... the Mary Whitney buried beneath it may not have any connection with Grace Marks at all. She could be just a name, a name on a stone, seen here by Grace and used by her in the spinning of her story."(451)

Through Dr. Simon, Atwood depicts the conversion of history into story. The primary plot is based on a famous nineteenth century murder case. In the summer of 1843, Thomas Kinnear, a gentleman farmer and Nancy Montgomery, who was both his housekeeper and his mistress, were murdered in Richmond Hill near Toronto. Kinnear had two other servants, James McDermott and Grace Marks who were charged with the murders and found guilty. The second plot starts when Grace Marks meets Simon Jordan sixteen years after the murder in the Kingston Penitentiary. Jordan wishes to examine Grace not only because she is believed to be a murderess but also because she suffers from amnesia. After a long debate that goes on between psychoanalysts, Grace gets her pardon on Tuesday, August 7, 1872 after twenty eight years and ten months. By fabricating all these historical details with the story, Margaret Atwood portrays a strong woman who silently fights against the male-dominated society, in her *Alias Grace*.

While narrating her life-story, Grace thinks of telling a lie to the society and tries to hide the events of her life. By doing this, she erases her past and escapes into the future. Margaret Atwood in this novel *Alias Grace*, fictionalizes history, past and present. Both historical documents and fictional ones contain the so called truths about Grace's character and the representations of her inner essence.

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